

Speculation on Photon Entropy during Refraction

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Sept. 29, 2023

Entropy is usually associated with probabilities (e.g. Shannon's entropy= $S = - \sum \text{Probability}(i) \ln\{\text{Probability}(i)\}$ which suggests there is some uncertainty in the problem, captured by S . Entropy, however, also seems to be associated with the evolution of a system in time. Historically, entropy was introduced through the first law of thermodynamics: $dE = TdS - PdV$, before there was any formula involving probabilities. Furthermore, a constant entropy, which applies to an adiabatic process, means the process is reversible in time.

In this note, we consider the case of a photon which is represented by a quantum wavefunction $\exp(-iEt+ip \cdot r)$, but is also reversible in the case of reflection/refraction, even from a moving interface. The wavefunction, we argue, is associated with probability in space-time and so there should be associated entropies (as we have argued in (1)), but at the same entropy should be constant as the motion is reversible. In (1), we considered Shannon's entropy for t and x and used $A1 |\cos(Et)|$ and $A2 |\cos(px)|$ over half a cycle as probabilities. We introduce a third entropy associated with time, but not E in this note.

Here, we focus on the case of refraction. For a stationary interface, E is conserved, but p changes. Thus there is a change in the uncertainty in x , but not in t and the process is reversible, with time S being constant. (The first law suggests that $S=\text{constant}$, which is keeping with time entropy, but not with spatial (x) entropy.) We suggest that there may be multiple types of entropy associated with different observables. We next consider the case of reflection/refraction from a moving mirror/interface. In such a case, neither E nor p is conserved for the photon. Both time and spatial (x) entropy change, but the process is reversible and entropy should be constant. We suggest there exists an entropy which is constant, but is based on: $-Et+ p \cdot r = t |p| (-E/|p| + \text{unit vector} \cdot r/t)$ where r/t vector is minus the velocity of the moving interface and the unit vector points in the direction of momentum p . We consider an associated entropy and the first law of thermodynamics.

The Notion of Entropy

Entropy is usually associated with probability, i.e. with some uncertainty in a problem. In particular, Shannon's entropy is defined as:

$$S \text{ (Shannon)} = - \sum \text{Probability}(i) \ln\{\text{Probability}(i)\} \quad ((1))$$

This definition may be applied to the tossing of a die or coin. It is not particularly associated with the evolution of a system in time.

Historically, however, entropy was associated with the evolution of a system in time. Even before there existed a definition of entropy, it was known that an object with kinetic energy loses some energy due to heat when moving over a surface with friction. This implies that the evolution (or motion) is not reversible. Clausius developed the first law of thermodynamics, without using probability, to deal with this irreversibility, i.e.

$$dE = TdS - PdV \quad ((2))$$

We suggest there are two aspects to entropy:

- (A) A probabilistic or uncertain view of an object
- (B) Evolution in time, in particular its reversibility or lack thereof.

(A) Immediately begs the question: What is uncertain or probabilistic in a problem?

Classically, one describes a particle by r vector, p vector, so for a large number of particles (gas), one considers the possible r vector, p vector arrangements and these lead to a notion of entropy. The entire gas system may evolve such that entropy remains constant (adiabatic process). In such a case, the evolution is reversible in time.

We argue that a free particle which does not interact is also reversible in time. This, it seems, suggests there exists some kind of constant associated entropy, but at the same there does not seem to be any probability or uncertainty.

Quantum Mechanics of a Free Particle

Even though a classical free particle does not seem to be associated with probabilities, a quantum free one is, through its wavefunction:

$$\exp(-iEt + p \cdot r) \quad ((3))$$

This suggests decoupled t and r vector variables, with probability associated with each. As we suggested in (1), there seems to be a Shannon's entropy associated with time and one with space. In a simpler form, ((3)) is: $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. We suggested in (1) using:

$$S(\text{time}) \text{ density} = -A1 |\cos(Et)| \ln\{|\cos(Et)|\} \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{and} \quad S(x) \text{ density} = -A2 |\cos(px)|$$

$$\ln\{|\cos(px)|\} \quad ((4b))$$

Here one considers a cycle or period, or even entropy over half a cycle. Different E, p values have different entropy densities.

A free particle moves in a reversible manner, so entropy should be constant as ((4a)) and ((4b)) are. What happens, however, in the case of refraction for which E remains constant, but p changes?

Quantum Mechanics and Refraction from a Stationary Interface

In one considers a stationary interface between two media, one with index of refraction $n_1=1$ and the other with $n_2>n_1$, then E (energy) of the incident and refracted photon is the same, but the magnitudes of the momenta (as well as their directions) differ. This suggests that time Shannon's entropy ((4a)) is a constant, but momentum Shannon's entropy ((4b)) is not. The process, however, is reversible and so should be associated with a constant entropy. This

seems to suggest that time entropy should be used to describe the reversible aspect of refraction. This does not mean that spatial entropy does not exist and does not change. It does, but it does not describe the evolutionary aspects of the process. This should be associated with a time related entropy.

We suggest one may use ((4b)) to describe two different spatial entropies even though there exists a constant time entropy ((4a)).

Moving Interface

What happens in the case of a moving interface? We suggest one needs to consider the wavefunction ((3)). Its phase may be written as:

$$-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r} = t |\mathbf{p}| \left\{ \frac{E}{|\mathbf{p}|} + \text{unit vector} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{r}}{t} \right\} \quad ((5))$$

Here $-\mathbf{r}/t$ is the velocity vector of the moving mirror (reflection) or moving interface (reflection/refraction) and the unit vector points in the direction of \mathbf{p} (momentum).

We have argued in previous notes that ((5)) is a constant for reflection/refraction. For a stationary interface, $-\mathbf{r}/t=0$ so this suggests that:

$$E_{\text{incident}} = E_{\text{reflected}} = E_{\text{refracted}} \quad ((6))$$

One may use ((4a)) to write a time entropy density for each which is constant and consistent with these representing reversible processes. In the case of a moving interface, it is ((5)) which is constant and again associated strictly with a time entropy, although one now has:

$$S(\text{Shannon time, moving interface}) \text{ density} = -A \left| \cos \left\{ t |\mathbf{p}| \left\{ \frac{E}{|\mathbf{p}|} + \text{unit vector} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{r}}{t} \right\} \right\} \right| \ln \left\{ \left| \cos \left\{ t |\mathbf{p}| \left\{ \frac{E}{|\mathbf{p}|} + \text{unit vector} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{r}}{t} \right\} \right\} \right\} \right\} \quad ((7)) \quad (A = \text{normalization constant})$$

((7)) is a type of time Shannon's entropy, but it is not the time Shannon's entropy, associated with $\text{Probability}(t) = \exp(-iEt)$. There seem to be three entropies in the photon reflection/refraction problem:

(A) Shannon's entropy associated with $\exp(-iEt)$ where E differs for the incident, reflected and refracted photons

(B) Shannon's entropy associated with $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ where \mathbf{p} differs for the incident, reflected and refracted photons

((C)) Shannon's entropy associated with the constant: $t |\mathbf{p}| \left\{ \frac{E}{|\mathbf{p}|} + \text{unit vector} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{r}}{t} \right\}$.

It is only ((C)) which describes the reversible nature of reflection/refraction from a moving surface. One may note that ((C)) is equivalent to using $\exp(-iEt + i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$, but one has to impose the further constraint of $-\mathbf{r}/t + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r} = t |\mathbf{p}| \left\{ \frac{E}{|\mathbf{p}|} + \text{unit vector} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{r}}{t} \right\}$. In other words, one ignores quantum fluctuations of t and \mathbf{r} vector and only focuses on $-\mathbf{r}/t$ vector = velocity of

the interface, with t still remaining as a fluctuating variable under this constraint. It is this associated special entropy which describes the reversibility of refraction/reflection and satisfies $d\{p| \{ E/|p| + \text{unit vector} \cdot r \}\} = 0 = TdS$ (no work).

If one considers only reflection from a moving mirror with speed $-v$ along the y axis and vertical refraction, then:

$$E_{\text{reflected}} = E_{\text{incident}} (c-v)/(c+v) \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{If } v \ll c, \text{ then } E_{\text{reflected}} = E_{\text{incident}} + dE \text{ where } dE = E_{\text{incident}} (-2v/c) \quad ((8))$$

Shannon's entropy density associated with E_{incident} is: $A \cos(Et) \ln(A \cos(Et))$ where $A = bE$, where b is a number. Then $S = \text{number}(no E) + \ln(E)$ and $TdS = T dE/E$. This suggests that for the first law to hold for refraction using the time entropy associated with $\exp(-iEt)$, $T=E$. In other words, even though this does not predict the reversibility of refraction, as entropy changes, it does seem to be consistent with the first law of thermodynamics if $v \ll c$ and $T=E$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that entropy is associated with two fundamental ideas, probability (uncertainty) and evolution in time (reversibility). These are usually applied to a gas, but we argue that time reversibility exists for a free particle or photon. Classically, however, these are not associated with probability, but, quantum mechanically, they are through wavefunction $= \exp(-iEt + i p \cdot r)$. We argue one may write two Shannon's entropies, one associated with time and a probability $A |\cos(Et)|$ and the other with $A^2 |\cos(px)|$ and representing space as argued in (1).

In the case of refraction from a stationary interface, one has time reversibility, so entropy should be constant. Only the time entropy listed above, however, satisfies this condition as spatial entropy changes because $|p|$ changes.

In the case of a moving interface, neither E nor $|p|$ is the same for an incident, reflected or refracted photon. There is, however, a constant in the system which follows from the wavefunction, namely: $-Et + p \cdot r = -t |p| (E/|p| + \text{unit vector} \cdot r/t)$ where $-r/t$ vector is the velocity of the moving interface. This expression is constant for the incident, reflected and refracted photons if one uses the respective E , $|p|$ and unit vector values. Here the unit vector lies along p . One may create a time-like Shannon's entropy which remains constant and indicates reversibility in time, namely ((7)). We note that a Shannon's entropy using the probability $\cos(Et)$ for reflection, with $E_{\text{reflected}} = E_{\text{incident}} (c-v)/(c+v)$ shows that $E_{\text{reflected}} = E_{\text{incident}} + dE$ if $v \ll c$. One may show that $dE = TdS$ with $T=E$ in such a case, but the changing entropy suggests a lack of reversibility in time, when, in fact, there is reversibility.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Maximum Entropy, Bias Removal, Conserved Quantity and Second Law of Thermodynamics (preprint, zenodo, 2023)

